

Supplementary Information

Supplementary Table 1. Sources of datasets

No	ID	Cytokine storm trigger	Cytokine storm non-trigger	Tissue
1	GSE182917	11	0	Lung
2	GSE183533	26	5	Lung
3	GSE150316	15	8	Lung
4	GSE171668	18	0	Lung
5	GSE166424	4	32	Blood
6	GSE155454	34	18	Blood
7	GSE152641	62	0	Blood

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

(E)

(F)

(G)

(H)

(I)

(J)

(K)

(L)

(M)

(N)

Supplementary Figure 1. Module Gene Ontology Biological Process Enriched Terms:
 A. Lung Blue, B Lung Dark Turquoise Module, C. Lung Light Pink Module, D. Lung Violet Module,
 E. Blood Tan Module, F. Blood Sky Blue 3 Module, G. Blood Turquoise Module, H. Blood Sky Blue
 Module, I. Blood Royal Blue Module, J. Blood Pale Turquoise Module, K. Blood Orange Module, L.
 Blood Light Cyan Module, M. Blood Dark Magenta Module, N. Blood Dark Grey Module, O. Blood
 Cyan Module, P. Blood Violet Modul

Supplementary Figure 2. Protein-Protein Interaction Network of Lung and Blood Modules.